

Sonia

THE "PROMOVENDUS"

*She is a PhD candidate in her 2nd year
She started her research with an assignment.*

Designed by nensuria / Freepik

She started her PhD with a state-of-the-art literature review, looking at what is already published in the context of her assignment. She follows the research method of her supervisor. She presents her first results in **posters** at **conferences**, in order to get accustomed to her scientific community.

Her audience is her group and other groups from the same **department**, with people having different expertise. But she works on finding her own **expert community** at conferences. She starts building expertise and addresses to **practitioners** in her field and to the general public. She understands the researcher's mission to a societal responsibility and she publishes **articles in specialised magazines**.

She has **no measured impact yet** in a traditional way because of the lack of scientific articles but she intends to have as much as possible scientific publications and increase her visibility. She is considering the succesful test of her model in the private sector as a method of evaluation of her work.

Sonia as a **SCIENTIST**

She has two published **conference proceedings**.
She has accounts on **Mendeley** and **ResearchGate**.

Sonia as a **DESIGNER**

She consider herself a scientist and a designer as her research outcome are **theoretical models**.

Sonia as an **ENGINEER**

She is making her own **code**.

Sonia as a **TEACHER**

She is quite active in teaching. She helps sometimes MSc students with their work. She's also involved in **coordinating feedback** giving to students in online courses and is even giving **lectures** - video recordings - in a MOOC.

"Our research should have an impact in the 'real world', otherwise we are just concerned about issues relevant for ourselves".

I miss "...reviews from all over the world (global perspective), which should show the importance of the topic."

She has mainly **conference posters** and **proceedings**.

Her network is local, in her **department** and growing beyond. She goes to **conferences** to learn the who is who in her field and build up an expert network.

She follows the **visibility strategy** of her group, but is less active than other colleagues. She is a **Mendeley** and **ResearchGate user**. The line between work and private use of **social media** is very well defined.

She publishes in **journals** with a high enough IF. She doesn't have an h-index yet.

Icons from www.onlinewebfonts.com

ALTMETRICS

She tweets when a paper is published in her group only. She is very aware of the use of social media for work but prefers mostly to stay offline.

She is aware of a social responsibility to communicate her work and writes in specialised magazines with a general audience. She intends to publish Open Access.

Alex

THE SCIENTIST

*He is an Assistant Professor
He starts his research with a question in mind*

Alex as a **SCIENTIST**

He publishes his **scientific results** and **data sets** in **journal articles** and **conference proceedings** mainly. He writes **reviews** in scholarly journals and is invited to sit on **editorial boards**.

He is choosing for **high IF journals** in his field to reach his audience. He has an account on **ResearchGate** because there he can put pre-prints versions of his article online for increased visibility for a large audience.

His **h-index** and **total number of citations** are important to him. He keeps track of his impact. **Uses** and **downloads** are not as interesting to him as who is interested in a particular paper or topic is. An **RG score** is not a quality indicator or a predictor for success, it is an indicator for network. He is recognised by peers in his field. His audience is mainly academic.

Open Access publishing is not "a limiting factor" for him. Publishing in a good journal to reach his audience is more important.

While the subject could be appealing to general public, people don't need to hear about equations and algorithms, the abstract work or the technical details.

His research results are sometimes shown via organised **events**, demo's, when the communication department invites **mass-media**.

Alex as a **DESIGNER**

He is designing solutions to complex problems in his field.

Alex as an **ENGINEER**

He is using algorithms and makes simulations. He is programming. His code is a tool that but it is not a product of his research: the ideas are in the code.

Alex as a **TEACHER**

His research results are present in the courses he prepares for his students as lecture materials, exercises or as examinations questions. The course is inspired by cases from research.

He has MSc students under supervision. Sometimes he works for **grant proposals** for education.

"Research is my core activity".

"The code in itself is a tool to test the ideas that we have in mind".

"If I get the feeling that without this [altmetrics] my chances to getting a project approved will decrease, then ..., ok, then it becomes important it's becoming a part of project aquisition"

He publishes **scientific articles** and **reviews**. He is invited to sit on **editorial boards**.

He goes to **conferences** and participates in **events**.

He writes **grant proposals** for education.

He has a **website** and is present online. He has a **ResearchGate profile** and an **RG score**. He uses **social media** mainly for personal matters. He **tweets** when a paper from his group is published.

He tracks his **h-index** and **citation score**. He chooses journals with **high IF**.

Icons from www.onlinewebfonts.com

ALTMETRICS

Alex wants to be visible and tracks his h-index - he likes a bit to "show off".

On his website, Alex would like people to know he is working on particular topics, to inform about the content. He doesn't need people to know he was mentioned in several places and how many times: it's distracting. If he is writing a project proposal, he finds it useful to let the funders know that a particular paper was mentioned online.

It would be great if he had someone who were blogging about what's happening in his group, about the every day frustrations or updating on wikipedia the status of his work with the latest technology because there's a new insight.

He is not sure if one can account altmetrics as a good indicator for a "measurable societal impact", he needs a convincing argument.

Mark

THE DESIGNER

He starts his research with a purpose in mind.

Mark as a DESIGNER

He deals with human factors and he is in search for utility.

The results of his research are diverse: **designs**, **3D models**, **books**, **booklets** for general public, **exhibitions** and (governmental) **strategies**.

His work appears in **mass-media** or in **governmental reports** and is a point of discussions in blogs. He receives **prizes** that bring him **recognition** and **funding**. He has a **Google Scholar** profile. He is actively reviewing on **Publons** and participates in collaborative writing on **GitBook**.

He is known by his peers, experts in the field but it happens many times that his work is reviewed by non-experts due to the **huge societal impact** of his work.

He makes a contrast between research and design by focusing on:

- objectives instead of questions
- innovation instead of discovery
- **usefulness** instead of impact

The work ranges from abstract to practical. The abstract work is published in journal articles or conference proceedings. The practical work, while having a low h-index, is very much visible in **mass-media**, as highly relevant to society.

*"In design what matters as impact is usefulness"
"Design - fit something to a purpose. How to evaluate that?"*

"If you want to capture what makes this community of the faculty of architecture special, you also have to look at the reputation of professors as designers, you should be able to track the importance of the design [...] There is no way that I can bring it forward!"

Mark as a SCIENTIST

He publishes as well scientific results and datasets mainly in journal articles and conference proceedings. His work is used and cited in high IF journals from his field.

He writes books. He writes reviews in scholarly journals. His h-index is relevant but does not cover all his research output. He is recognised by peers in his field.

Mark as an ENGINEER

His designs are mostly materialised in prototypes and demonstrations and in case of success, final products. In some cases, Mark's designs are models and simulations. He develops code and maintains software tools.

Some of his code is for internal use only, and some of the code is published on **GitHub**.

Mark as a TEACHER

His research is present in the courses he prepares for his students and in the course textbooks. He has MSc students under supervision. Sometimes he works for grant proposals for education.

He makes **designs** and **models** and he writes **books**. His name appears in **mass-media**. He publishes **reports** in governmental projects with significant societal impact.

He organises **events** and participate in **exhibitions**.

He receives **prizes** that bring him **recognition** and **funding**.

He is visible on **Google Scholar** and his name appears in **blogs**. He is a reviewer on **Publons** and publishes code on **GitHub**.

He tracks **metrics** on his **Google Scholar profile** - which is "very sensitive to societal impact".

Icons from www.onlinewebfonts.com

ALTMETRICS

He considers that design is a very competitive field. But as a designer, he gets praised often by non-peers.

His research is delivering much more than scientific articles or conference proceedings. His works have impact onto society but it is not properly measured.

He would like a new metrics for usefulness to be added to the impact. He doesn't trust one number describing the societal impact.

Metrics do not measure the quality of the work - that can only be decided through peer-review.

He doubts how useful aggregating a number of weighted factors are, if we we don't have a sight of how this works for real people.

Anne

THE ENGINEER

She's an innovator!

Anne as an ENGINEER

She is implementing a design into a material, a prototype, a model or a final product.
She works in a **highly innovative environment**.

Her research results are very important for the business and industrial sector. She is giving **workshops** and participates in **events** organised by companies so that she gets fast the newest developments.

In her field, people work part-time in academia and part-time in spin-offs or in other companies. The information they are looking for cannot be found in scientific databases - those are a slow lane of information for them.

Her work requires up-to-date information in a very dynamic industrial landscape. She profiles herself as an expert in the field by publishing in **professional magazines**. As a result, she collaborates with companies, which leads to **projects** - investments in her research.

She publishes occasionally open access. However, in an innovative environment with partners in industry where she can apply for **patents**, this is a limited option.

Anne as a SCIENTIST

She is doing research and is publishing journal articles. She is mostly interested in **conference communications** and networking because of the need to be up-to-date as fast as possible. Her h-index is not very relevant to her interests. She produces **reports** in joint projects with the industry. She is known by her peers.

Anne as a DESIGNER

She designs innovative solutions to existing problems. These solutions can vary from an abstract level to a very practical one, with high relevance to the society.

Anne as a TEACHER

Her research outcomes are used in **courses** she develops.

"...you are happy to be part of such group [committee] because then you get super fast information... They published the report, that was this year, but in 2014 I had the first meeting. So, that was three years afterwards that I could find out what was in the report..."

"People from practice [...], they are not interested in publishing."

Her name appears in **professional magazines**. She has **patents**. She works in an **innovative environment**.

She goes to **conferences, meetings** and **events**, to reach fast information from government, businesses and industry. She helps organise **workshops** and **symposia**.

She writes **project proposals** (with partners from the industry.)

She has a **website** and is present online on Google Scholar.

She doesn't really track her **metrics** - her h- index is not representative for her work.

Icons from www.onlinewebfonts.com

ALTMETRICS

Anne wants to be visible in the academic, but mostly in the business and industrial environment. The h-index brings her only to her academic community. Her research results and expertise can be found only in professional magazines.

She wants to be able to see her societal impact.

She doesn't trust one number of weighted factors to calculate impact. But she welcomes any metrics that can increase her visibility along with mentions related to the quality of her research.

Femke

THE TEACHER

*She is an Assistant Professor
She starts her teaching
with learning objectives in mind*

Femke as a **TEACHER**

Her research results are present in **lecture materials, exercises** or **examinations questions** and **feedback** for students. All these are available in the standard **offline courses** she prepares for her students, as well as in the **online courses** or **MOOC's**, on Open Courseware or edX platforms. She writes **textbooks** and **guidelines** for students who need to orient themselves in the variety of existing methods. She has **BSc, MSc students** and **PhD candidates**.

She is as well **coaching** her students, sometimes in **one-to-one sessions**. She is working with students in intensive **project-based programs**, alternating theory with practice, to deliver the students her know-how and experiment till they can work independently. She is also learning from the students. She transforms the teaching - learning interactions in **win-win situations**. She is determined to make both teaching and learning a positive experience.

She considers the first year students have difficulty understanding that teaching is conveying a type of understanding and learning is something they have to do themselves. Her difficult task is to bring the student to a university level of **conceptual thinking**. The discipline comes secondary to the personal development in thinking. Therefore, the **impact** of a teacher can not be seen immediately but later on, when the student can acknowledge the influence a teacher had in his behavior and maybe in life.

She teams up with colleagues, in well defined course programs. The discussions with fellow teachers keep all of them sharp in reaching to the goal of the course.

Femke as a **SCIENTIST**

She publishes **books** and **scientific articles** and uses them as references in the courses she gives. There are articles published, about the experiences of students in new learning environments. These are used for designing new teaching methods.

Femke as a **DESIGNER**

She is **creative** in her teaching and blends research with education in different forms of **interactions**. Sometimes she makes **playcards** or **fun quizzes** for students. She innovates new environments of collaboration between practitioners and students.

Femke as a **ENGINEER**

She is building tools and applications of her designs working together with her students. She creates and teaches while they learn by doing.

...“Passing grades should be a story not only numbers”...

“The fact that there are young people who need to take over our society withing a few years... it's so important that they are well trained! I think it's undervalued!”

“I like teaching because I learn myself”

She writes **books** and **textbooks** based on her research. She makes her own **lecture materials, assignments**, gives **feedback** to the students from her **online** and **offline courses**.

She collaborates with fellow teachers in **educational projects**, sometimes giving **intensive courses** abroad.

She writes **grant proposals** for education.

She is not publicly visible for her teaching work. She could receive a student award “The best teacher of the year”.

Traditionally, teachers receive written-only feedback from students at the end of courses (online and offline) used to improve the following course. In more modern approaches, the students are interviewed and a study is published.

Icons from www.onlinevectorfont.com

ALTMETRICS

How to measure impact? “In research you have countable measures that you can debate, but we have them. The number of students: only the best teachers can teach 300 students. Because of the potential impact that you have! Like the best researchers get the biggest grants - and it's something that we don't have in place.”

“After 10 years they will remember us and will be happy! A short-time hapiness doesn't say anything about learning”.

Educational skills count but the human factor in teaching is important and this is difficult to quantify.

She would like her innovative approach in teaching to become visible and recognised. She would like her performance in teaching to be considered for her career development in clear steps.

She would like her students to know about different activities she does, like being invited in editorial boards.

David

THE STRATEGIST

He is an Associate Professor

David as a STRATEGIST

He takes care that people in his group publish articles in the right **scientific journals** in order to reach the community, or in **professional magazines** to profile themselves for the practitioners.

He takes care of **networking**, getting people together by participating and organising specialised **workshops** at conferences and **events**.

His groups communicates **strategies** and **policies** in **reports** that are written in a language for a large (public) audience.

His group has an up-to-date **website**.

He involves the communication department for his group visibility, that invites **mass-media** in case of events or demo's interviews.

He has a **group visibility strategy** with the target of getting **recognition** and **funding** for his group.

David as a CONSULTANT

He has to publish in **professional magazines**, to stay up-to-date, to keep the industry and governmental partners informed about his expertise.

He is writing **books** as an authority in his field.

He is invited to discussions in **workshop panels** for the government.

He involves his groups in **projects** with the industry and the government from where he gets **funding**.

David as a MANAGER

He takes care of the **career development** of his people. The **Tenure Trackers** are in his responsibility.

He hires people based on their total number of citations, **h-index**, their **network**, their **performance in projects** or their **presence at exhibitions**.

He judges the **potential** for the job of the new candidates.

"I see the whole presenting of research results as secondary to the networking"

"A metric to show the expertise in the field would be good"

"In the case of the creative work of our professors architects, [...] their contribution to the body of knowledge of architecture, [...] is not captured."

"I like to keep track of everything"

He writes **books** and makes **strategies**. He appears in **mass-media**. He publishes **reports** in governmental projects with huge societal impact.

He take care of networking, he organises **events** and his groups participate in **exhibitions** with partners from industry or government.

He develops **strategies** that bring him and to his group **recognition** and **funding**.

He developed a **visibility strategy** for himself and his group.

He tracks **metrics** of the people from his group and applicants.

Icons from www.onlinewebfonts.com

ALTMETRICS

David wants his group to be visible. He has a strategy, but he would like structural help with that.

He is ambivalent on measuring the impact, he thinks that some things are just part of the job.

He is interested in societal new metrics for his group to be added to the impact of an individual.

He doesn't trust one number describing the societal impact.

He wants metrics for the activity of his group and its positioning in his field of expertise. He would like to have a map of experts (expertise) to find and to be found easily.

His new researchers could add to his group a new network of people and a new audience.